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SHARQ GAVHARI XIVA SHAHRIDA MA'MUN UNIVERSITETI NODAVLAT TA'LIM MUASSASASINING FAOLIYATI

O'zbekiston hududida sivilizatsiya va davlatchilikning shakllanishida qadimiy madaniyat o'choqlaridan biri Xorazm muhim o'rin tutgan. Binobarin "O'zbek davlatchiligining tamal toshlari bundan 2700 yil muqaddam ayni Xorazm vohasida qo'yilgan. Shu ma'noda, milliy davlatchiligimiz tarixi Misr, Xitoy, Hindiston, Yunoniston, Eron kabi eng qadimiy davlatlar bilan bir qatorda turadi. Xorazm tarixi o'zbek davlatchiligiga oid ulkan ma'lumotlar, moddiy va yozma yodgorliklar to'plangan tarixni asosi, uning qudrati va qadimiyligining tasdig'idir".

Davlatchilikka asos solinishi uchun, avvalombor, huquqiy asos bo'lishi kerak va shu ma'noda Xorazmda huquq ilmi ham shu davrlarda shakllangan. Shuningdek, Xorazm zaminidan yetishib chiqqan ilm-u fan namoyondalari yaratgan asarlar jahon tamadduni xazinasiga qo'shilgan katta hissa ekanligi barchamizga ma'lum.

Bu borada ayniqsa, XI asr boshida tashkil etilgan Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi (Majlisi ulamo) allomalarining qomusiy ilmiy faoliyati jahon ilm-fani taraqqiyotini yangi pog'onaga ko'taradi, bu faoliyat rakursini kengaytirib yubordi. Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi jahon ilmiy tafakkur tadriji, madaniy va ma'naviy taraqqiyotining benazr durdonasi sifatida tarixda chuqur, o'chmas iz qoldirgan.

Dunyo sivilizatsiyasi tarixida bunday markazlar o'zining mustahkam asoslariga, qadimiy ildizlarga egadir. Jumladan, insoniyat tarixidagi ilk akademiya, Aflotun akademiyasining "Bog' suhbatlari" – olimlarining turli mavzular bo'yicha bahs-munozalar shaklida voqelangan bo'lsa, keyingi davrlardagi ilmiy markazlar olimlarning doimiy ilmiy faoliyati bilan shug'ullanuvchi uyushmalariga aylangan. Ushbu an'analar islom davrida yangi bosqichga ko'tarilgan. IX asrda Bag'dodda tashkil topgan ikkinchi akademiya – "Bayt ul-hikma" Sharqning to'ng'ich akademiyalaridan sanalib, mazkur ilmiy dargohda ijod qilgan olimlarning aksari, jumladan, Muhammad al-Xorazmiy, Ahmad al-Farg'oniy, Ahmad al-Marvaziy, Abbos al-Javhariy va boshqalar Movarounnahr zaminidan yetishib chiqqan taniqli allomalar va mutafakkirlar edi. Ular tomondan yaratilgan bebaho asarlar va ilmiy kashfiyotlar keyinchalik Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi olimlar jamoasining nazariy va amaliy ilmlar sohasida erishgan yutuqlari uchun ma'naviy asos bo'lgan edi.

Tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, O'rta Osiyoda IX asrgacha shahar madaniyati beto'xtov rivojlanib, IX-XII asrlar ushbu o'lka xalqlari uchun buyuk yuksalish davri bo'lgan. Xorazm hukmdorlarining faol harakati tufayli XI asrning ikkinchi yarmida Ma'muniy xorazmshohlar davlati vujudga kelib, mamlakatning siyosiy, iqtisodiy va madaniy jihatdan yuksalishi davri bo'ldi. Ayniqsa, Ma'mun ibn Muhammad (992-997), Ali ibn Ma'mun (997-1009) davrida Xorazmda davlat mustaqilligi mustahkamlanib, uning harbiy qudrati oshdi. 1004-yildan Beruniyning Gurganchga kelishi bilan Xorazmshoh saroyida olimlar davrasi tezlik bilan to'la bordi va bu davrni Ma'mun akademiyasining to'la shakllangan, gullagan davri deyish mumkin. Abu Mansur as-Saolibiyning guvohlik berishicha, Gurganchda to'plangan faqat arabiynavis adiblarning o'zi 200 ga yaqin bo'lgan.

Tarixdan ayonki, vatanimizda taraqqiyotning yangi davri boshlanishi aynan Ma'mun asos solgan va Sharqning mashhur allomalarini bir dargohga jamlab, ularga zarur shart-sharoit, imkoniyat, imtiyozlar yaratib bergan 1004-yildagi "Dorul hikma", "Majlisi ulamo", ya'ni akademiya

tarqalgan ilm nurlaridan boshlanadi. Ma'munning hukmdor sifatidagi, davlat yuritishdagi huquq va siyosatdagi tafakkuri, ilm-fan namoyondalarini ezgu g'oyalar tevaragida birlashtirdi. Bu ezgu g'oya esa ko'p o'tmay jamiyatda o'z natijasini ko'rsatdi va matematika, astronomiya, kimyo, tibbiyot, huquq, geodeziya singari shu davrga xos barcha fanlar rivojlanib, Birinchi renessansga asos bo'ldi. Bunda o'z bag'riga daho mutafakkirlarni to'plagan oliy ma'rifat maskani – Ma'mun akademiyasi muhim rol o'ynagan edi.

Jahon ilm-u fanining e'tirof eshiticha, “Dor-ul hikma va maorif” (Ma'mun akademiyasi) nomini olgan mazkur ilmiy muassasa nafaqat Sharq balki butun dunyo uchun ham ahamiyatga egadir. Zeroki, ushbu dargohda Beruniy (973-1048), Ibn Sino (980-1037), Abu Mansur Ibn Iroq (958-1036), Abu Sahl Masihiy (970-1042), Abul Hayr Ibn Hammor (942-1018), Abu Mansur as-Saolibiy (961-1038), Abu Ali Ibn Miskovayh, (vafoti 1030), Abdulhakim Muhammad ibn Abdulmalik as-Solih, Al-Xorajiy, al-Hamdamiy, abu Abdulloh Al-Biyan Al-Naysaburiy, Ahmad Ibn Muhammad as-Suhayliy al-Xorazmiy, Ahmad ibn Muhammad as-Sahriy, Mahmud Hamid Ibn Xidr al-Xo'jandiy kabi ko'plab fan namoyandalari ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borishgani, tarixiy fakt va ular yaratgan asarlar tamaddun taraqqiyoti tadrijida muhim o'rin egalladi.

Akademiyasi allomalari Yunoniston, Yaqin Sharq va Hindiston, O'rta Sharqda erishilgan ilm-fan yutuqlarini ijodiy, tanqidiy, qiyosiy tahlil qilib, uni yanada yuksak bosqichga ko'tarishgan. Aynan ana shu allomalarning ilmiy faoliyati, asarlari tufayli Qadimgi Xorazmning san'ati, adabiyoti, astronomiyasi, matematikasi, sug'orish madaniyati yutuqlari jahon tamadduni xazinasiga kirgan va butun insoniyat manfaatlariga xizmat qila boshlagan.

Mustaqillik yillarida tarixda chuqur iz qoldirgan tabarruk ilm dargohining qaytadan Xorazm zaminida barpo etilishi dunyo olimlari, ilm-fan jamoatchiligi tomonidan olqishlandi, iliq kutib olindi. YUNESKOning 2004-yilda “Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasining 1000 yilligini nishonlash to'g'risida”gi qarori esa O'zbekiston hududi azaldan ilm-ma'rifat o'chog'i, ziyo markazi bo'lgani, bu an'ana bugun ham davom etayotganining jahoniy e'tirofi bo'ldi, albatta.

Davlatimiz rahbari Shavkat Mirziyoyevning 2017-yil yanvar oyida Xorazm viloyatiga, xususan, Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasiga tashrifi davomida bergan topshiriq va ko'rsatmalari respublikamiz olimlariga ham ko'rsatilgan hurmat-ehtirom namunasidir. Tabiiyki, bu ajdodlarimiz qoldirgan bebaho ilmiy merosdan unumli foydalanish barobarida, ilmiy yangilik va kashfiyotlar qilish, innovatsiyalar yaratish, yoshlarni ilmga jalb etib, iqtidorli, dunyo tan oladigan yagi avlod olimlari yetishtirishga katta ishtiyoq uyg'otadi.

Bugungi kunda Xorazm ramziga aylangan Xiva shahri haqidagi ilk ma'lumotlar X asrga oid arab sayyohlari asarlarida uchrasada XVII asr boshlariga kelib yirik shaharga aylanadi. Xiva xonlari davrida davlatdagi ilm-fan, adabiyot va san'atga qiziqish yanada yuksaladi. Shaharda saroy, hovli, karvonsaroy, masjid, hammomlardan tashqari ilm, ma'rifat ulashguvchi madrasalar, qorixonalar, kichik yoshli bolalar uchun xususiy uy maktabxonalari qurila boshlandi. Bu jarayon, ayniqsa, XVII asrda nihoyatda avj olib, XIX asrda o'zining cho'qqisiga chiqdi. Xiva shahridan tashqari butun xonlik hududida katta va go'zal peshtoqli madrasalar, atrofi bir yo'la ikki qavatli hujralar bilan o'ralgan hovlisi, masjidi va minorasi bo'lgan madrasalar qurildi. Tarixiy ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, XIX asr boshlarida faqat Xiva shahrining o'zida 120 madrasa va 63 qorixona faoliyat olib borgan bo'lib, rus bosqinidan so'ng ular soni 64 taga, 1922-yilga kelib 54 taga kamayganligini ko'rish mumkin. Mazkur madrasalarda islom dini va huquqidan tashqari, arab va fors tillari, tibbiyot, geografiya, musiqashunoslik, falsafa, tabiiy bilimlar kabi dunyoviy fanlar o'rgatilar edi. Madrasalar davlat idoralari uchun mutaxassislar, maktabdor va san'atkorlarni tayyorlab berdi.

Mustaqillik sharofati bilan Xorazmda ilm-fanga bo'lgan e'tibor yaxshilandi. XI asrda faoliyat olib borgan “Majlis ul-ulamo”ning vorisi sifatida Xiva shahrida Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi 1997-yil 11-noyabrda Birinchi Prezidentning maxsus farmoni asosida qayta tashkil qilingan bo'lsa, 2006-yilda uning 1000 yillik yubileyi keng miqyosda nishonlandi. Mazkur tadqiqot muassasasining ochilishi Xorazmda tarix, arxeologiya, manbashunoslik, filologiya, tuproqshunoslik, qishloq xo'jaligi kabi mintaqa uchun zarur bilimlarning rivojiga ta'sir qildi. Jumladan, 2500 yildan ortiq tarixga ega bo'lgan Xumbuztepa arxeologik yodgorligining ochilishi va uning quyi qatlamlari miloddan avvalgi VII-VI asrlarga oidligi isbotlanganining o'zi fikrimizning yaqqol misolidir.

Yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek, ulkan ilmiy meros va tarixga ega bo'lgan Xorazm va uning ajralmas bir qismi hisoblangan Xiva shahrida bugungi kunda ham ilm-fanga e'tibor yildan yilga ortib bormoqda. Xivada tashkil qilingan Ma'mun universiteti ulkan ilmiy salohiyatning mantiqiy davomi sifatida faoliyatini boshlaganiga hali ko'p bo'lgani yo'q.

Dunyo afkor ommasining e'tibor va e'tirofiga ega bo'lgan hamda shu davrda yaratilgan boqiy asarlari bilan hanuz tamaddunga xizmat qilib kelayotgan olimlarni o'z dargohiga to'plagan, ilm-fan homiysi, o'z davrining Metsenati hisoblangan, ma'rifatparvar Ma'mun nomi bilan ataladigan universitet qisqa davr ichida respublikada o'z nufuziga, obro-e'tiboriga ega bo'ldi. Muassasa yildan yilga o'z maqomini mustahkamlab borayotgani kishini quvontiradi.

Ushbu ta'lim dargohi bugungi kunda 7 mingga yaqin talablar tahsil olayotgan, Xiva shahrida faoliyat olib borayotgan dastlabki va hozircha yagona zamonaviy universitet sifatida o'z mustahkam o'rniga ega bo'lib ulgurdi. Bugungi kunda universitetda ikki yuzdan ortiq malakali professor-o'qituvchilar (shundan yuzga yaqini ilmiy darajali) ta'lim jarayonlari bilan bir vaqtda o'zlarining ilmiy faoliyatlarini Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi va boshqa ilmiy tashkilotlar bilan hamnafas, hamkorlikda olib borishmoqda.

Mamlakatda xususiy oliy ta'lim muassasalarining ochilishi nafaqat oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'rtasidagi raqobatni kuchaytirishga, balki hududlarning iqtisodiy ahvoriga ham o'z ta'sirini kuchaytiradi. Xususan, hozirgi kunda Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda 210 ta OTM mavjud bo'lib, undan 65 tasi nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari bo'lsa, 30 tasi xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari va ularning filiallari hisoblanadi. Bundan ko'rishimiz mumkinki, mamlakatimizdagi jami oliy ta'lim muassasalarining deyarli yarmi nodavlat va xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari hissasiga to'g'ri keladi. Bu, albatta, quvonarli holat, ya'ni abituriyentlarga keng tanlov imkoniyati yaratildi. Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi oliy o'quv yurtlari o'rtasida nafaqat talabalarni o'ziga jalb etish uchun raqobatni rivojlantirdi, balki ilmiy salohiyatli va bilimli bo'lgan professor-o'qituvchilarni o'ziga jalb etish bo'yicha ham o'zaro raqobat muhiti shakllandi. Natijada, o'qituvchilik kasbining maqomi oshdi, uning qadri ko'tarildi, ish haqlari oshirildi, ularga bo'lgan munosabat o'zgardi, eng asosiysi, o'qituvchilarda o'z-o'ziga ishonch, kasbiga bo'lgan ichki hurmat tuyg'usi mustahkamlandi, ilmiy tadqiqot olib borish uchun ijodiy muhit sifati yaxshilanib, natijada ishtiyoq oshdi.

Mamlakatimizdagi nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari faoliyat olib borishi uchun yaratilgan sharoitlar va berilayotgan imkoniyatlar natijasida nafaqat poytaxtimizda, balki hududlarda ham nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'z faoliyatini boshladi va buning natijasida hududlarning iqtisodiyoti, aholining turmush darajasi, turizm salohiyati, investitsion jozibadorligi oshdi. Xususan, davlat rahbarimiz boshchiligida ta'lim muassasalari va pedagog-xodimlarga yaratilayotgan sharoitlar va imkoniyatlar natijasida Xorazm viloyatida ham nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi uchun yetarli sharoitlar va imkoniyatlar yaratildi va buning natijasida hozirga kunda viloyatda 3 ta nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari va 1 ta xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasasi filiali faoliyat olib bormoqda.

Ma'mun universiteti viloyatdagi oliy ta'lim muassasalari orasida talabalar kontingenti bo'yicha 2-o'rinda (1-o'rinda UrDU), nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari orasida esa 1-o'rinda turadi. Ma'mun universitetining asosiy binosi viloyat markazidan 30-35 km. masofa uzoqlikda joylashganligiga qaramasdan, hozirgi kunda ushbu universitetda 7 mingdan ortiq talaba kunduzgi va sirtqi ta'lim shakllarida tahsil olib kelmoqda. Yana bir quvonarli tomoni shundaki, universitet talabalari tarkibi nafaqat viloyatimiz aholisidan, balki respublikamizning deyarli barcha hududlari aholisidan tashkil topgan. Viloyatimizda bunday oliy ta'lim muassasasining faoliyat olib borishi nafaqat yoshlarning oliy ta'lim bilan qamrab olish darajasini oshishiga olib keladi, balki ularning bilimi, fikrlashi, dunyoqarashi kengayishiga olib keladi, hududning madaniy-maishiy saviyasiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Hududlarda nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi iqtisodiy jihatdan bevosita o'sha hududning rivojlanishiga, yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmining oshishiga, aholi bandligini oshishiga, aholi turmush tarzining oshishi, hududlarda xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi faoliyati, turizm faoliyatining rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Ma'mun universitetining Xiva shahrida faoliyat olib borishi

natijasida, nafaqat tumanning, balki viloyatning iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy ahvoriga o'zining ijobiy hissasini qo'shib kelmoqda. Jumladan, universitet faoliyat olib borishi natijasida ikki yuz ellikdan ortiq yangi ish o'rinlari ochildi, universitetga har yili 20 dan ortiq xorijlik professor-o'qituvchilarning jalb etilishi natijasida turistik xizmatlar hajmi oshdi, respublikaning boshqa hududlaridan professor-o'qituvchilar va talabalarning jalb etilishi natijasida ichki turizm rivojlandi, hududdagi savdo va xizmat ko'rsatish sohalari deyarli 1,5-2 barobarga oshdi, xorijlik ilmiy salohiyatli olimlarni jalb etish orqali xorijiy mamlakatlar bilan hamkorlik aloqalari rivojlanishiga erishildi.

Eng samarali reklama insonlarning yaqinlariga qilgan reklamasi (jonli reklama) ekanligini hisobga olgan holda, viloyatimizga, universitetimizga tashrif buyurgan har bir mehmonda universitetimiz faoliyati, viloyatimiz, respublikamiz iqtisodiyoti, aholi turmush darajasi, urf-odatlarini, tarixiy obidalarini, bayramlari, ovqatlari haqida ijobiy xulosalarni shakllantirishga erishsak, kelajakda ular nafaqat ta'lim berish uchun, balki o'z yaqinlari bilan birga dam olish maqsadida ham tashrif buyurishlari mumkin.

Universitet oldiga qo'ygan asosiy maqsadlardan biri bu – barcha talabalarni to'liq grant asosida, bepul o'qitish tizimini joriy etish, dunyoning eng rivojlangan oliy o'quv yurtlari mingtaligiga kirish va Ma'mun universiteti brendini yaratish, Ma'mun ta'lim klasterini joriy etish hisoblanadi. Bu borada universitetimizda bir qator ishlab olib borilmoqda va "Ma'mun universiteti-2030" strategiyasi bo'yicha yo'l xaritalari ishlab chiqildi. Bunday natijalarga universitetda "Universitet 3.0" modelini to'liq joriy etish va bosqichma-bosqich "Universitet 4.0" modeliga o'tish orqali erishish rejalashtirilgan.

Ushbu ko'zlangan maqsadlarga erishmaguncha universitet jamoasi izlanishdan, harakatdan, ilm olishdan, ilm o'rgatishdan to'xtamaymiz va rejalarni amaliyotga joriy etish orqali, mamlakatimiz rahbarining, talabalarning, xalqimizning oldidagi majburiyatimizni bajargan va ularning ishonchini oqlagan bo'lamiz.

Barchamizga ma'lumki, har qanday jamiyatning ravnaqi, ijtimoiy, siyosiy, iqtisodiy barqarorligi o'sha yerda istiqomat qiluvchi fuqarolarining aqliy va axloqiy salohiyatining qay darajada rivojlanganligi bilan bog'liq. Zero, jamiyatning ma'naviy kamoloti, ijtimoiy yashash tarzi, kognitiv rivojlanganlik darajasi shu davlatning milliy mentaliteti yuksalishida, shuningdek, kadrlar tayyorlashning milliy masalasida ham ustuvor mezon hisoblanadi. Inson kamolotida, uning farovonligi va shaxsiy manfaatlarini ro'yobga chiqarishda hamda kerakli ijtimoiy xulq-atvor andozalarini shakllantirishda kasbning ahamiyati katta hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, bugungi kunda rivojlanayotgan psixolog mutaxassislariga bo'lgan talab davr talabi sifatida yaqqol namoyon bo'lmoqda. Inson bolasi kamolga yetgani sari ilmga, ma'rifatga talpinadi. Shu nuqtayi nazardan saboqni doimiy ravishda ijtimoiy muhit ta'sirida o'zlashtirib boradi. Bugungi shiddatkor jamiyatda psixolog kasbiga bo'lgan talab aynan inson omili bilan ishlashda, uning ta'sir obyektining butun hayotidagi ahamiyatini hisobga oladigan bo'lsak, shaxs kamolotida turli xil muammolarning yuzaga kelishi va uning yechimi bilan faoliyat olib borishda ko'rinadi.

Jamiyatda shaxsning shakllanishi insonning o'z aqliy qobiliyatlari jismoniy imkoniyatlari u yoki bu sohaga bo'lgan layoqati, qiziqish va intilishlari, shuningdek, qadriyat va dunyoqarashiga ko'ra belgilanar ekan, inson omilining aynan shu jihatlarni shakllanishi va rivojlanishida salbiy omillarning ta'sirini bo'lmasligini cheklay olmaymiz, chunki hayot tarzi turli xillik bilan bog'liqligidan tashqari, inson shaxsi rivojlanishidagi ehtiyojlari, individual psixologik xususiyatlari, atrof-muhit ta'siri kabilar murakkab hayot tarzining dolzarb muammolaridan biridir.

Bu o'rinda Ma'mun universiteti o'z oldiga psixolog kasbiga tayyorlanadigan mutaxassislarni har tomonlama yetuk, eng avvalo, boshqalarga yordam berish ko'nikmasini shakllantirish bilan birga o'z shaxsiy muammolarini oldindan ko'ra bilish va uni hal qila olish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lgan mutaxassislarni tayyorlashni o'z oldiga maqsad qilib qo'ygan. Chunki, inson shaxsida, turli yoshdagi kishilar bo'lgan jamoaviy munosabatlarda, kasbiy faoliyatga moslashish, yangi ijtimoiy rolni tushunib olish har bir inson hayotida yangi muammolarni keltirib chiqarishini hisobga olgan holda bu mezonlarga e'tibor qaratish hamda jahon amaliyotining muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan, shuningdek, zamon talablariga mos keladigan jahon andozalari asosida mutaxassislikka tayyorlashga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev tashabbusi bilan jamiyatimizda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar, tabiiyki inson qadrini oshirish, uning huquq va manfaatlarini himoyasini kuchaytirishdek ezgu maqsadga yo‘naltirilgan. Aynan shu tufayli ham davlat rahbarining siyosiy irodasi bois huquqiy demokratik, adolatli jamiyatda, ilm-u fan rivoji uchun ilmiy-pedagogik jamoalarga zarur shart-sharoit, imkoniyat yaratib berilmoqda. Negaki, davlatimiz rahbari ta’kidlaganlaridek, “Biz o‘z oldimizga mamlakatimizda Uchinchi Renessans poydevorini barpo etishdek ulug‘ maqsadni qo‘ygan ekanmiz, buning uchun yangi xorazmiylar, beruniylar, ibn sinolar, ulug‘beklar, Navoiy va boburlarni tarbiyalab beradigan muhit va sharoitlarni yaratishimiz kerak”, degan da’vatiga hamohang olib borilayotgan tizimli yangilanishlarning amaldagi in’ikosidir.

Agarki tarixdagi jarayonlarga nazar solib, tahlil etadigan bo‘lsak, davlat boshqaruvida olib borilgan odil siyosat, davlatning ilm-ma’rifatga, olimlarga e’tibori, ta’lim-tarbiya ustuvor etib qo‘yilgani o‘tmishdagi Uyg‘onish davriga xos eng muhim jihat bo‘lgan.

Aynan shu ma’noda, so‘nggi yillarda Yangi O‘zbekistonda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarni, ayniqsa, ilm-fan, ta’lim sohadagi innovatsion yangilanishlar, olim va ziyolilarga yaratib berilayotgan shart-sharoitlar, yoshlar ta’lim-tarbiyasi yo‘lida bajarilayotgan beqiyos ishlarni ma’rifatparvar Xorazmshoh Ma’muni ibn Ma’mun, Ali ibn Ma’munning, adolatparvar Sohibqiron Amir Temurning tamoyillariga qiyoslash mumkin. Ya’ni, bugungi davrimizda o‘tmish bilan bugun va kelajak uyg‘unlashgan holda yana Renessanslarga xos tamaddunga zamin yaratilmoqda.

Shu ma’noda Ma’mun universitetining o‘tmishdagi Ma’mun asos solgan, rivoj toptirgan akademiyasi singari dovuq tarqatishi borasidagi o‘z sa’yi harakatlarimizda dadil boraveramiz.

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THE DEVELOPMENT ISSUES OF PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATION IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Private higher education refers to educational institutions that are not funded by the government and rely on tuition fees, endowments, donations, and other sources of funding to operate. Private universities and colleges are often established by individuals, religious organizations, or corporations, and they may have a more specialized focus than public institutions. Private higher education institutions often have smaller class sizes, more personalized attention from faculty, and more specialized programs than public institutions. They also tend to have greater flexibility in their curriculum and can respond more quickly to changes in the job market and industry demands. Private institutions often offer more resources and opportunities for internships, research, and networking, which can be beneficial for students' career prospects. However, private higher education institutions are often more expensive than public institutions, and tuition fees can be a significant obstacle for many students.

Key words: public institution, beneficial, specialized programs, financial aid, scholarship, curriculum.

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YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA XUSUSIY OLIY TA'LIMNING RIVOJLANISH MASALALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Xususiy oliy ta'lim deganda davlat tomonidan moliyalashtirilmaydigan va o'qish uchun to'lovlar, vaqflar, xayriyalar va boshqa moliyalashtirish manbalariga tayanadigan ta'lim muassasalari tushuniladi. Xususiy universitetlar va kollejlarda ko'pincha jismoniy shaxslar, diniy tashkilotlar yoki korporatsiyalar tomonidan tashkil etiladi va ular davlat muassasalariga qaraganda ko'proq ixtisoslashgan bo'lishi mumkin. Xususiy oliy ta'lim muassasalarida davlat muassasalariga qaraganda ko'pincha sinflar kichikroq, professor-o'qituvchilarning shaxsiy e'tibori va ixtisoslashtirilgan dasturlari ko'proq. Ular, shuningdek, o'zlarining o'quv dasturlarida ko'proq moslashuvchanlikka ega va mehnat bozori va sanoat talablaridagi o'zgarishlarga tezroq javob bera oladilar. Xususiy muassasalar ko'pincha talabalarning martaba istiqbollari uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan

amaliyot, tadqiqot va tarmoq uchun ko'proq resurslar va imkoniyatlar taklif qiladi. Biroq, xususioliy o'quv yurtlari ko'pincha davlat muassasalariga qaraganda qimmatroq va o'qish to'lovlari ko'plab talabalar uchun jiddiy to'siq bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: davlat muassasasi, foydali, ixtisoslashtirilgan dasturlar, moliyaviy yordam, stipendiya, o'quv rejasi.

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ВОПРОСЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЧАСТНОГО ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В НОВОМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Частное высшее образование относится к учебным заведениям, которые не финансируются государством и зависят от платы за обучение, пожертвований, пожертвований и других источников финансирования. Частные университеты и колледжи часто создаются отдельными лицами, религиозными организациями или корпорациями, и они могут иметь более специализированную направленность, чем государственные учреждения. Частные высшие учебные заведения часто имеют меньшие размеры классов, более индивидуальное внимание со стороны преподавателей и более специализированные программы, чем государственные учреждения. Они также, как правило, имеют большую гибкость в своем учебном плане и могут быстрее реагировать на изменения на рынке труда и требования отрасли. Частные учебные заведения часто предлагают больше ресурсов и возможностей для стажировок, исследований и налаживания связей, что может быть полезно для карьерных перспектив студентов. Однако частные высшие учебные заведения часто дороже государственных, а плата за обучение может стать серьезным препятствием для многих студентов.

Ключевые слова: государственное учреждение, льготные, специализированные программы, материальная помощь, стипендия, учебная программа.

INTRODUCTION.

Higher education has a long history, it appeared in Eastern countries, like Egypt, Babylon, and China, a system of higher education was born a few thousand years ago. In high schools, students studied the works of scientists about the laws of development of nature and society, ways of managing the state. Thinkers such as Plato (428-348 BC) and Aristotle (384-322 BC) justified the fact that the physical and mental capabilities of each person are fully manifested in 3-level education. [7;78-79] That is why in Greece and Ancient Rome, the need for the third, higher stage of education for free people and children of nobles was recognized. Philosophy, philology, music, oratory, medicine, mathematics in ancient higher education, special attention is paid to studying sciences. As in many countries of the Muslim East, the first higher education in Turkistan was provided by madrasahs. They played a decisive role in the emergence of the stage called the Muslim Renaissance in the history of mankind. By the 11th-12th centuries, the first forms of the higher education system in the modern sense began to appear in Western countries. [5; 89-96] During the renaissance, great scientific discoveries in fields such as mathematics, mechanics, astronomy, navigation, and medicine led to the deepening of the content and expansion of the scope of higher education. Higher education progressed in proportion to the development of science, technology, culture and art. Higher education in the current sense was provided to local residents of Uzbekistan under the leadership of Munavvarqori, the founder of the Central Asian Jadid movement, at the People's School, which was established in Tashkent on May 12, 1918. [1; 32-45] Although the network of higher education expanded somewhat during the period of the Soviets, the training of highly educated personnel from the local population was not in a stable position. Private universities often foster environments conducive to innovation

and entrepreneurship. They can nurture an entrepreneurial spirit among students and faculty, supporting innovative research, technology transfer, and startup incubation programs. This emphasis on innovation can lead to the development of groundbreaking research and the advancement of knowledge. Private universities often attract a diverse student body from various backgrounds, cultures, and regions. This diversity can enrich the educational experience by promoting cultural exchange, international perspectives, and the ability to learn from a wide range of perspectives. Additionally, private universities may provide a supportive environment that celebrates diversity and cultivates inclusivity.

METHODS AND THE LEVEL OF STUDY.

After Uzbekistan gained independence, higher education began to develop rapidly. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" (1997), higher education is based on the basis of secondary special or vocational education and has two stages - bachelor's and master's degrees. Until a certain period of the implementation of the national personnel training program, higher education is also carried out on the basis of eleven years of general secondary education. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, which practices freedom of religious belief, there are also secular higher education institutions and higher religious education institutions. Higher education in Uzbekistan is under the control of the state. University higher education has a priority status in the country. This allows the specialists to acquire world-class theoretical knowledge and practical training. Higher education is carried out on the basis of official state documents. State standards of education, curricula are of decisive importance in this. Subjects that are compulsory and theoretical to be studied in them, specialization courses, their training order, amount, time, the ratio between theoretical and practical education, theoretical training, training and production practices, rating period, vacation, bachelor's qualification work, master's theses defense the term is determined in the main pedagogical document - the curriculum. Subjects studied in the curriculum are divided into such parts as humanitarian and socio-economic, mathematical and natural-scientific, general professional, specialized subjects and additional types of education. It is envisaged that subjects in the curriculum will be conducted in compulsory, special and optional forms. The development of private higher education in Uzbekistan is a relatively new phenomenon, as the country has only recently begun to transition to a market-oriented economy. While private higher education institutions (HEIs) have existed in Uzbekistan since the early 1990s, they have faced significant challenges in terms of funding, regulation, and public perception. [12; 78-80]

One of the primary challenges facing private HEIs in Uzbekistan is funding. Private institutions typically rely on tuition fees and private donations for their funding, while public HEIs receive significant state support. This can make it difficult for private HEIs to compete with public institutions in terms of resources and quality of education. Another challenge facing private HEIs in Uzbekistan is regulation. The government has historically been suspicious of private institutions, and has imposed strict regulations on their establishment and operation. For example, private HEIs must obtain a license from the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, and must meet certain requirements related to faculty qualifications, curriculum, and infrastructure. Additionally, private HEIs in Uzbekistan have faced challenges related to public perception. There is a widespread belief that private institutions are inferior to public institutions, and that they exist primarily to make money. This perception has made it difficult for private HEIs to attract students and faculty, and has limited their ability to establish themselves as legitimate institutions of higher education.

Despite these challenges, there has been some progress in the development of private higher education in Uzbekistan in recent years. The government has taken steps to streamline the licensing process for private HEIs, and has provided some support for the development of private institutions. Private HEIs have also begun to establish themselves in niche areas, such as business and technology, where they can offer specialized programs that are not available at public institutions. In general, the development of private higher education in Uzbekistan is still in its early stages, and there are significant challenges that must be overcome. However, with continued support from the government and a growing recognition of the value of private institutions, there is potential for private HEIs to play an important role in the development of higher education in Uzbekistan. Private higher education

institutions (HEIs) are institutions of higher learning that are not operated by governments. They are typically funded by tuition fees, private donations, and endowments, and may offer a variety of academic programs and degrees. Here are some examples of private HEIs:

1. Harvard University: Located in Cambridge, Massachusetts, Harvard is a private Ivy League research university that is widely regarded as one of the top universities in the world. It was founded in 1636 and has a long history of academic excellence.

2. Stanford University: Located in Stanford, California, Stanford is a private research university that is known for its strong programs in engineering, computer science, and business. It was founded in 1885 and has produced many notable alumni, including Elon Musk and Larry Page.

3. New York University: Located in New York City, NYU is a private research university that is known for its strong programs in the arts, humanities, and social sciences. It was founded in 1831 and has campuses in New York City, Abu Dhabi, and Shanghai.

4. Liberty University: Located in Lynchburg, Virginia, Liberty is a private, Christian university that is known for its conservative values and strong programs in business, law, and education. It was founded in 1971 and has grown rapidly in recent years.

5. Keiser University: Located in Fort Lauderdale, Florida, Keiser is a private university that is known for its career-focused programs in fields such as nursing, criminal justice, and business. It was founded in 1977 and has campuses throughout Florida and online. These are just a few examples of the many private HEIs that exist around the world. Private institutions can offer a wide range of academic programs and opportunities, and can be a good choice for students who are looking for a more specialized or personalized education. Private higher education institutions (HEIs) in Uzbekistan have several advantages over public institutions. Here are some of the advantages of private HEIs in Uzbekistan:

1. Flexibility: Private HEIs in Uzbekistan have greater flexibility in terms of curriculum development and program offerings. They are not subject to the same bureaucratic constraints as public institutions, which allow them to respond more quickly to changes in the labor market and to offer programs that are more tailored to the needs of students.

2. Quality: Private HEIs in Uzbekistan are typically smaller than public institutions, which allow them to provide more individualized attention to students. They may also have more modern facilities and equipment, and may be able to attract more highly qualified faculty members.

3. Innovation: Private HEIs in Uzbekistan are often more innovative than public institutions, as they are not bound by tradition or government regulations. They may be more likely to experiment with new teaching methods, technologies, and program offerings, which can benefit students and the broader education system.

4. Networking: Private universities in Uzbekistan may offer students greater networking opportunities than public institutions. They may have closer ties to the business community, which can lead to internships and job opportunities for students.

5. Specialization: Private HEIs in Uzbekistan may be more specialized than public institutions, offering programs in areas that are not covered by public institutions. This can be particularly beneficial for students who are interested in niche fields or who have specific career goals.

The draft of the Constitutional Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was announced. It is noteworthy that Article 50 of the Draft Constitutional Law states that "The state ensures the development of the continuous education system, its various types and forms, and state and non-state educational organizations." Determining the issue of ensuring the development of non-state educational organizations at the level of the Constitution eliminates the assumptions that they may disappear or may be closed later by a decision. In particular, Article 16 of the Draft Constitutional Law stipulates that "No law or other regulatory legal document may contradict the principles and norms of the Constitution."

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

I can proudly say that on April 12, 2021, a wonderful event took place in the city of Ancient Khorezm, that is, the first private university was established. It is no exaggeration to say that Arslonbek Nurjanov, the founder of the Mamun Institute of World Languages, has created wide

opportunities not only for the youth of Khorezm, but also for the youth of the world. On 14.01.2022, the Institute of World Languages named after Mamun was changed to Mamun University NEI. Currently, many reforms are being implemented by the founder of the university, Arslonbek Nurjanov.

Today, a center for awarding the "TRKI C1" - "Language" certificate level was opened at the university under the license of the People's Friendship University of Russia RUDN in the direction of "Russian language", and the Russian language teachers of the whole region passed a week of training. , can take a 5-level exam and get certificates right here. This is the first permanently operating contract center in Khorezm region. At the same time, the introduction of the Hemis system in a short period of time, the material and technical base, computerized rooms, surveillance systems, Face control system, professionalism in education and others are the reasons why Mamun University stands out. A single identification number, which is planned to be established soon, will ensure that students or teachers participate in classes and inspections completely electronically. This increases responsibility and quality. In addition, it is envisaged that students belonging to social protection (true orphans, children of orphanages, those who have lost their breadwinners) will be admitted to the university on a grant or half-grant basis. However, students who have shown results due to their diligence (TRKI C1, CEFR C1 or IELTS 7+) are also accepted on the basis of a grant. Such students will not only be exempted from paying contract fees, but will also be provided with a scholarship. This is a great motivation for our students.

Our international relations are also developing rapidly. Last year, we signed a Memorandum with the Korean Language Center, which enables cooperation with South Korean universities. On the basis of the contract, Yong Kwan Goo conducts classes in "Korean language". This year we signed a contract with "Dicle" University of Turkey. We are about to be involved in the "Erasmus" project. In addition, Professor Shaydurov Vladimir Nikolayevich worked in the main field of history this year based on our contract with the Russian state "Leningrad State University". At the same time, we made a business trip to Belarus on March 13-16 and participated in the "Belarus-Uzbekistan Scientific Forum". We signed contracts with four of the universities that demonstrated their capabilities at the forum (Grodno, Vitebsk, Belarusian National Technical University and Belarusian University of Food and Chemistry). [3; 22-27] These leading universities are among the top 1000 universities in the world. In particular, "Belarusian Food and Chemistry" University offered to train students in the Master's degree. For this, it was emphasized that qualified teachers can come or conduct online classes, as a result of which the student will be able to get a diploma of 2 state universities. One of the main reasons for this is the achievements of Mamun University in a short period of time. The students of our university will be ambitious students who will try to get deep knowledge for their bright future. Only then will it be made up of students who will understand that they will have a wide range of opportunities.[3; 25,26]

I imagine that our students who graduate from the university will be educated, strong, and will have a distinct place in the labor market. It is certainly not easy, but our current policy allows us to create such a future, because we are trying to do so. Many foreign universities maintain ties with their graduates and retain their staff. It will be a great result if we form their union and help them find a job. students who graduated abroad work in high positions, organize funds, contribute to the development of the university, organize book funds and scholarships. For example, Harvard University produced 10 presidents, 100 senators, Nobel laureates, 100 presidents and directors of companies, and these people also contributed to the development of their universities.

CONCLUSION.

Private universities often have higher tuition rates than public universities, but they may offer students more financial aid and scholarships to cover their costs. In addition, private universities may have smaller student groups and receive individualized attention from professors.

It is important to note that each private university has its own unique characteristics, strengths, and weaknesses. Prospective students should thoroughly research and consider multiple factors - such as program offerings, faculty expertise, location, reputation, facilities, financial aid options, accreditation, and student support services - when evaluating which private university aligns best

with their academic and personal goals. While private universities may have higher tuition fees compared to public institutions, many provide generous financial aid packages and scholarships to eligible students. These financial aid programs aim to make quality education more accessible and ensure that deserving students have the opportunity to pursue their higher education goals. Private universities often have more autonomy in decision-making processes compared to public universities. This autonomy allows them to be more agile and responsive to changing educational needs and trends. They can adapt their programs, develop new curricula, and respond to market demands more quickly and efficiently. They often specialize in specific fields or disciplines, offering programs tailored to meet industry demands and individual interests. They may provide focused and rigorous training in areas such as business, arts, technology, healthcare, or humanities, positioning graduates to excel in their chosen fields. Private universities typically have smaller class sizes compared to public institutions. This allows for a more intimate learning environment where students can engage in interactive discussions, receive personalized attention from faculty members, and actively participate in hands-on learning experiences. The smaller campus communities often foster strong student-faculty relationships, mentorship opportunities, and a sense of belonging.

Overall, private universities in Uzbekistan can offer students a range of advantages, including greater flexibility, quality, innovation, networking opportunities, and specialization. However, it is important for students to carefully research private institutions before enrolling, to ensure that they are reputable and that their programs meet their needs and career goals.

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